

THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF MAJID QORI QADIRI

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Abstract: In this article, no matter how much our people suffered from national oppression and social injustice during the colonial period, no matter how much they suffered, they were never depressed. Looking to the future with complete confidence, it is said that he has consistently fought for freedom and freedom against national oppression and colonialism in various forms.

Key words: Society, modernity, education, freedom, national idea, spirituality.

Majid Qari Qadiri (Kadyrov) (Russian: Маджид Кадыри (Kadyrov)); real name Abd-ul-Majid-khan Qari Abd-ul-Qadir-khan Qari son of мжид гарі кадри (Russian: Abd-ul-Majid-khan Kary Kadyri; May 2, 1886, Qori-Yogdi neighborhood, Shaykhantohur district, Tashkent - October 4, 1938, Yunusabad (now the site of the "Martyrs' Memorial" complex, Tashkent) - Uzbek scientist, writer, first published in Uzbek the author of textbooks, in particular textbooks of literature, history and arithmetic, one of the founders of the modernist movement in Turkestan.

Majid Qadiri (Qadirov) was born in the family of an imam in the Qori-yogdi neighborhood of Tashkent's Shaykhantohur district. First, he studied in the old method school, and then in the madrasa. He started teaching in "usuli-savtiya" (old method) and then "usuli-jadidiya" (new method) schools, later he worked in madrasas and Russian-tuzem schools. He knew Persian, Arabic, Turkish, Russian and English languages. 1906 He began to teach mathematics in Russian schools from 1917, before the Red Revolution in 1917, he taught and was the headmaster of secondary schools in Tashkent. In 1918-1921, he was the headmaster of the 6th Turon school founded by the Jadidist movement. From 1918, he became a member

of the Communist Party. In 1920-1921, he was the head of the Pedlaboratory of Nature and History in Tashkent. In 1921 he taught at the Boy Scout School in Tashkent. participated as (Decisions issued by the first national Uzbek language and spelling congress, which was held in January 1921. - Tashkent.: State publishing house of the Republic of Turkestan. - 1922.) He started teaching Uzbek language. In 1921-1923, he was the dean of the "Working Faculty" of the Turkestan State University, and at the same time he was the head of the "Research" laboratory of the Turkestan State University. He was awarded the title of "Hero of Labor" on March 23, 1923. In 1923-1925, he was the director of the Nature Conservation Museum. In 1924, he was an employee of the Tashkent Foundation branch. went as a representative of the newly established Republic of Uzbekistan. On his way to Paris, he stopped in Berlin and met with Uzbek students studying in Germany. In 1928, he headed the "Physics Department" at the Central Asian State University. In 1928-1930, he held the position of dean and head of the history department of the "Working Faculty" of the Central Asian State University. He was expelled from the party in 1929 and dismissed from his job at the beginning of 1930. His expulsion from the party and his dismissal were caused by the slanders of some proletariat and pro-Soviet people and the columns published in the press in 1929-1930. Majid Qadiri continued to teach at the Central Asian State University after 1930. In 1937, he was arrested by the NKVD of the USSR as an "enemy of the people". In the investigative work, it was officially written that he was arrested on April 2, 1938. On September 12, 1938, Prigovar was sentenced to be shot by the "troika" of the NKVD. The bloody day was October 5, 1938 (AP RF, op. 24, delo 418, list 114). 507 of the most reformers of the Uzbek nation were condemned as "enemies of the people" on this day, and they were executed in the White House in Yunusabad. shot at the top. After independence, the "Martyrs' Memorial" complex was built in this place. On February 13, 1958, he was found innocent by the Military Collegium of the USSR - "posthumously rehabilitated" and re-incorporated into the Communist Party. Majid Qadiri first printed in Uzbek and applied arithmetic to education in new-style schools (Majid Qori, "Hisob (Basics of Elementary Education in Mathematics)

Volume 1"), Tashkent 1910 (in 1913 and 1915 by the publishing house "Turkistan Kutubonus" reprinted), "Hisob 2-Juz", Tashkent 1914, geography (Majid Qori, "Jugrofiya", Tashkent 1911) and grammar books in Chigato-Turkish (Uzbek) language. Saidrasul Aziziy, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Muhammad Rasuliy, Shokirjin Abdurahimjanov, and others participated in publishing activities. The successful development of the educational process in the new-style schools was hindered by the lack of a single teaching methodology at that time. The same issue was discussed by the representatives of the intellectuals for the implementation of the school education reform, who gathered in May 1914 in the house of the Shayhantohur daha qazi, asking for the introduction of advanced national textbooks and textbooks. . The participants of the meeting emphasized the success of the school education process and the way to get rid of problems in the transfer of students from one school to another. At the meeting, the members of the committee responsible for the development and implementation of the unified educational methodology were confirmed, including teachers of the new method school: Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Qori Samig Ziyoyev, Shokirjon Muhammad Rasul Abdulloh Avloni, proofreader of the newspaper "Sadoi Turkistan" and teacher of the Russian-Tuzem school. correction Worked at that time: a meeting of schools novometodnyh teachers, including the selection of a competent committee for the development of a unified curriculum Russian-system schools Abdul Majid Qori Qadiri were approved (Central Archives of the Republic of Uzbekistan. fund R-461, 1 volume , 1260 case , 22 sheets). The Jadids of Turkestan made a great contribution to the reformation of traditional sciences along with the introduction of secular sciences in educational institutions and provided invaluable support to poor families who wanted to learn. Thanks to their efforts, the "Turon" charity fund was established in Tashkent, "Tarbiyai atfol" in Bukhara, "Gayrat" in Kokand, more than ten enterprises, publishing houses, and libraries were established. The founders of the first charitable foundation "Jamiyati Khairiya" founded in 1909 were Munavvarqari and Avlony. On the basis of this society, in 1913, the "Turon" society was organized by the intellectuals and wealthy people of Tashkent. On the basis of this society, the

"Turon" drama troupe, the "Turon" library and study hall, and the "Turkistan library" publishing house were established. The community-based "6th Turon" school was headed by Majid Qadiri from its establishment in 1918 until he moved to the Turkestan State University in 1921. In 1923, in the January 1 issue of the "Turkistan" newspaper, in order to promote new style educational programs It was announced that "Publishing-Maarif" society was established. The founders of this society were Munavvar-Kori Abdurashidkhanov, Mannon Ramz Shokirjon Rahimi, Zahiriddin a'lam Elbek, Shahid Eson, Salimkhan Tillakhanov, Hamid Sulaiman, Holmuhammad Ohundi and Majid Qadiri. was an ardent supporter of liberating the Uzbek people. .Professor Naim Karimov in his article "Founding Jadidism as the basis of the national idea" describes Turkestan Jadids as follows: "The best representatives are the best representatives of Jadidism, they certainly served the people and the Motherland. Their entire lives were devoted to a great historical mission - to shed light on the oppressed people, to show them the way to a happy life, to instill a sense of self-respect and pride, and to instill in them a sense of ownership of the land where their ancestors lived." and remained in people's memory as a child of the great Uzbek people and a hero of his time.

The name of Majid Kadirov (Majit Kadirov) was included in "Stalin's shooting lists" of the Uzbekistan SSR. This list includes high and mid-level leaders who worked in the field of party, national economy, military and science. The lists were compiled by the NKVD authorities after the investigation was completed and sent to the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the CPSU(b) for approval. With the approval of 2-5 members, it was sent to the Military Committee of the Supreme Court of the USSR for "legal formalization" with investigative work. The lists were divided into categories, category 1 (they made up the main bulk) were those sentenced to death by firing squad. The military panel of the Supreme Court (in this case - its visiting session in Tashkent) issued a verdict without the participation of a prosecutor and a lawyer in the so-called special order of the court. A maximum of 20-30 minutes was allocated for consideration of the case, without the possibility of

appeal against the decision, and it was carried out with the execution of the sentence within hours. The list including Majid Kadiri was approved by Stalin, Molotov and Zhdanov on September 12, 1938. (Information provided by Memorial Foundation in 2009).

Conclusion. Every new era moves towards development with the change of human thinking, outlook, and understanding. As the gradual progress in social life, scientific achievements raise the spiritual world of human society, its own history, values, his views on civilization and perspective will expand. This article also mentions that Majid Qari Qadiri studied Persian, Arabic, Ottoman Turkish, Russian and English languages, despite the difficulties of being engaged only in science.

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